

Smile!

*A Guide to Healthy
& Happy Teeth*

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Happy Teeth*

The D.R. Moon Memorial Library

Teeth are very important. They make the shape of our face. They help us to smile, chew, and talk.

To do their job, we need to make sure to take care of them!

Have you ever been told to brush and floss?

I bet you are wondering why it matters, and there is more to it than only preventing cavities. Germs from the mouth are connected to every other part of your body, for example, your joints and heart.

If your gums and teeth are healthy, the rest of your body can become healthier too.

Tooth Anatomy

The outside of a tooth is called enamel. It is hard and like a bone.

The next layer of the tooth is called dentin.

The inside of the tooth is called the pulp chamber. It is filled with blood vessels and the nerve.

The part of a tooth we use to bite and chew is called the crown.

A tooth has a root that connects to the jaw bone.

The root and jaw bone are covered by gums.

Bad germs called bacteria form on teeth. These germs can stick and make plaque. This can happen only an hour after brushing and flossing.

When plaque mixes with spit, also known as saliva, calculus can form. This is hard and harder to clean off a tooth than plaque.

Plaque and calculus together make gums hurt. You can see this when gums bleed when you brush, floss, or have them cleaned at a dentist. If gums hurt for a long time it can make the jaw lose bone.

To keep our teeth, gums, and body healthy,
we need to:

- Take time to clean
- Brush twice a day
- Floss at least once a day
- Clean tongue twice a day

This can seem like a lot but it is the best way to
keep your teeth and yourself healthy.

Brushing and flossing are important for overall health and to not get cavities. Cavities are a disease from bacteria getting into deep layers of teeth over time and can have a variety of causes.

For example eating lots of foods rich in carbohydrates, like bread or sweets...

or acidic foods and drinks like lemonade, can cause cavities.

How to Brush:

When you brush, spend 5-10 seconds gently making circles on each part of each tooth. Remember to wait thirty minutes after a meal to brush.

To clean under the gumline of your top teeth, tilt your toothbrush up a little.

For your bottom teeth, tilt the toothbrush down a little.

How to Floss:

Gently place the floss between two teeth and slowly guide through until it is just above the gums. Be careful not to pull the floss through hard because this can hurt the gums.

Pull the floss against one tooth and move the floss up and down 3-7 times.

Move the floss above the gums once again and pull against the other tooth and repeat.

Toothpaste that has mineral ingredients like fluoride can make the enamel of our teeth stronger. This helps us not get cavities. Chewing gum that has xylitol, a fake sugar, can help do the same.

While it is important to have good oral hygiene, it is also important to see a dentist. Dentists help to find and treat cavities, gum disease, and even cancer. It's a good idea to visit your dentist twice a year to watch for any problems and keep your mouth healthy and happy.

Smile!

Activities

I BRUSH MY TEETH

Brush and floss every day to keep your teeth healthy. Color a tooth every day that you brush and floss. Make it a habit for a healthy smile!

Name:

Date:

Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun

TOOTHPASTE TANGLE

Which string of toothpaste finds its way to the toothbrush?

TOOTH MAZE

Remember to floss your teeth everyday.
Can you help get the floss all the way around the tooth?

START

LUNCHBOX WORD SEARCH

To have a healthy smile, it helps to choose foods that aren't sugary treats.
Can you find all the hidden words?

O K O R A N G E E M W N R O S
R L B R E A D S H A U S Q C T
A I Z T S L T I T D C A P E R
N M Y A Q O J E G B D N R L A
G R E T R Y R K V A S A E E W
E F P R G M F O N E K N T R B
J S A Z E U A B I Y L A T Y E
U C M L P L C R E J A B U Z R
I Y O E M V R K E S V I B O R
C N X O W E R Y C E O C T T I
E G N A B U O A U P C H U O E
F D Q E T G H P T A A E N M S
S D U V U X C P T R D E A A H
I L K R S W B L E G O S E T X
B J T L M N U E L R W E P O T

- | | | |
|---------------|-------------|------------|
| TURKEY | MILK | ALMONDS |
| PEANUT BUTTER | CHEESE | APPLE |
| STRAWBERRIES | GRAPES | AVOCADO |
| CARROTS | CELERY | TOMATO |
| BANANAS | BLUEBERRIES | WATERMELON |
| YOGURT | LETTUCE | ORANGE |

TEETH TO TREASURE!

WORD SEARCH CHALLENGE!

See how many words you can find in 20 minutes!

Words go across, up, down, and diagonal.

K E F Q J S P M O D K R D G C Q T M T E
M Z K L D W E B O T P O H R K S E O C U
X D G M O F C L S U C O B T I W O R E Q
D A I L Y S W N B A T T D T J T S L D A
A S G L E B S O V A J H N B H W P P I L
H C E K I L C I F S T E G B E N I R R P
E T S A P H T O O T D E R U J J L E O G
P J U V L Y M F C S L U G A A N N V U J
T D L E M A N E U Z S E O E Y R E E L U
O E O O X B N G O H Y V F R V M D N F F
B F V Q A E A T K X V L J T A P K T A U
A S U N U R Y P X P K L A D F L E I K P
C L N G W Q H T O O T E H N R Q T O V H
C S N I H V L G K Z M W A J U B P N A X
O O M I A N X G I X A N A F I X P Z R H
T F I U A R V U C Z K H Z U T Z B A L D
U I U Y G C G C P P B V X K P J Y S R Z
P R I M A R Y Z A T E K Y L V P I R F J
I I U J M I L K I K M O G N T L Z I L B
B Q L X O I W D L A E H V L E U Z L I E

CAVITY

DAILY

DENTIST

ENAMEL

FLOSS

FLUORIDE

FRUIT

GRAINS

GUMS

JAW

LIPS

MEAT

MILK

MOUTHGUARD

ORAL

PLAQUE

PREVENTION

PRIMARY

ROOT

SEALANT

SUGAR

TOBACCO

TONGUE

TOOTH

TOOTHBRUSH

TOOTHPASTE

VEGETABLES

XRAY

WORD PUZZLE

Find the missing word in each sentence, then write it in each box.
Combine the first letter in each word to uncover the hidden word!

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--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

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1. Certain types of bacteria found in some of the f_____ you eat can stick to the enamel that covers your teeth.

2. L_____ to floss your teeth takes time and patience. If you're just beginning to floss your teeth, be sure your mom or dad or another adult is there to help you.

3. Floss at least o_____ a day and take your time to be sure you've flossed in between every tooth.

4. Brushing your teeth at least twice a day helps get rid of some of the plaque on your teeth. Be sure to brush the tops, s_____, front, and back of your teeth.

5. The dentist puts s_____ on your teeth to seal out food and plaque to protect you from cavities.

6. It is i_____ to clean between your teeth in places where your toothbrush can't reach.

7. Brushing alone is n_____ enough to keep your teeth healthy.

8. Brushing with toothpaste helps remove plaque from your teeth and g_____.

CROSSWORD CHALLENGE

Across

2. A food, deep yellow inside, belonging to the vegetables group
4. A primary cause of cavities and gingivitis
8. The innermost tissue of a tooth
11. With good personal and professional care, you should keep your teeth as long as you are ____ .
13. This booklet is about ____ health.
14. A liquid containing calcium
15. The thin, hard covering of the root of a tooth
16. Most dentists recommend a tooth brush with soft _____ .
17. A product that is bad for your total health
18. A food with a white inside, belonging to the vegetables group
20. A natural substance which can help prevent cavities
21. A member of the grains group, frequently eaten in Asian countries
22. A watery secretion that bathes teeth and promotes digestion
23. Used to remove plaque

Down

1. The most common dental disease among young people
3. Protects teeth during sports
5. The periodontal _____ holds the tooth in its bony socket.
6. The hard outer covering of a tooth
7. Coating that protects teeth from decay
9. The part of the mouth just outside the teeth
10. A good substitute for meat
11. The type of bone in which teeth are embedded
12. _____ disease can result in destruction of tissues surrounding the tooth.
18. A fuzzy-skinned member of the fruits group
19. The front teeth
20. Cleans between teeth

(Your Name)

has completed this booklet on oral health!

TO BE AN ORAL HEALTH ACE, REMEMBER TO:

- Brush your teeth two times each day
- Floss your teeth daily
- Eat fruits and vegetables instead of sugary foods
- Visit your dentist regularly

HERE ARE A FEW THINGS I LEARNED:

1

2

3

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